

The Impact of Chinese FDI on Infrastructure Development in the Selected African Countries

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Abstract

this study aims to investigate the impact of Chinese FDI on infrastructure development in selected African countries. The empirical analysis estimates by using a panel data approach for a set of African countries spanning from 2003-15. These empirical estimation has been carried out through fixed effects technique. The findings of the study reveal that, Chinese investment has a positive impact on infrastructure development in the sample countries. Based on study findings, it is safely concluded that Chinese investment and infrastructure quality move parallel in the sample countries.

Key Words: Foreign Direct Investment, Infrastructure Development, Panel Data

JEL Classifications: F21, E21, C23

Introduction

The stock and quality of infrastructure is a main ingredient of growth and development in both developed and developing countries. An increase in infrastructure raising productive capacity through aggregate demand during the construction phase. Several existing studies (Beaton, Cebotari, & Komaromi, 2017; Calderón & Servén, 2004; International Monetary Fund, 2017) supports the positive relationship between infrastructure development and growth. An improvement in infrastructure increases the volume of exports (Cerra & Woldemichael, 2017) and also surge the quality of export products (Ding & Hadzi-Vaskov, 2017). In most of developed countries, infrastructure quality is so high but varies across the regions in developing countries.

This study enlightened the flow of Chinese FDI in African countries. FDI and infrastructure development both are playing a significant role in the development of every nations. FDI is an important source of infrastructure development which assists to enhance infrastructure status in a country. On the other way, infrastructure improvement is an important factor to attract foreign investment in host country. A good and quality infrastructure is considered as the backbone of various sector, industrial production, agriculture and economic growth of a country. FDI helps to fill up the financial gap between the funds needed to sustain a level of growth and availability of domestic funds. FDI brings abundant funds and modern technologies which helps in boosting the economic growth.

Several existing studies argued that, well-developed infrastructure is a good determinant to attract FDI inflow in developing countries. Hence, there are also some factors apart from good infrastructure which affect FDI inflows such as, market size, banking and financial system, political and economic stability and has also a positive impact on economic growth. Whereas, a couple of existing studies concluded that, stock and quality of good infrastructure is consider as main contributing factor to attract more FDI inflow. Their findings reveal that, infrastructure development is essential for the developing countries.

Ari and Toivanen (2005) recognised that, financing is a big challenge and lack of financing is hold back the development process. The development of infrastructure is crucial to positively affect economic growth and these development reducing the cost of production, transport. Hence, facilitating trade and communications. Their findings furtherly reveal that, less-developed infrastructure hamper the growth potentials in existing countries.

The present study exists the impact of Chinese investment in infrastructure development of various sectors such as, telecommunications, transportation and education. The findings of the study reveal that Chinese FDI has a positive impact on infrastructure development in selected African countries (Kumari and Sharma, 2015).

Literature Review

The availability and reliability of good infrastructure are consider as an important contributing factor of economic growth of the developing countries. The Chinese investment activities in Africa has created the attention of researchers and policy makers (Besada et al., 2008; Broadman, 2007; Cheung and Qian, 2009b; Goldstein et al., 2006; Li, 2007, and Wang, 2007),

The existing studies examine a strong positive relationship between FDI and infrastructure development. As investment in infrastructure is increased, will lead to attract foreign capital and increased the incentive of multinationals to invest in the growing economy (Globerman and Shapiro, 2002). Coughlin et al. (1991) argued that investment in transportation were associated with increased FDI. In a similar line, Wheeler and Mody (1992) examined that good infrastructure in developing countries is a crucial determinant to attract FDI from the developed countries. Similarly, Ranade (2001) examined that infrastructure expenditure like roads and highways have a positive role on economic growth and improve private investment.

Zafar (2007) argued that, a substantial amount of Chinese FDI is improved infrastructure in the African countries. In the last two decades, China has been one of the fastest growing economies. China is playing a crucial role in the world economy. In 2005, China is GDP is almost 18.2 trillion Yuan (\$2.25 trillion) and its share is increasing in the global output. China exports has dramatically increased in the last five years. The presence of Chinese workers in the global market has been doubled with amount of 100 million workers. Chinese ODI in African countries pay the attention of both policymakers and researchers.

From the last two decades, the economic expansion of China with Africa are going to become very clear. China built a strong network of trade, aid and investment links with African countries. Several Chinese multinationals invest in different countries like extracting oil in Angola, building roads and highways in Ethiopia, improved electricity and line distribution in Kenya, boost tourism industry in Sierra Leone and in telecommunications (mobile network services) upgraded in both Kenya and Nigeria. Chinese companies playing a vital role in the development of infrastructure (dams, ports and roads). For instance, Cheung et al. (2011) claim that, Chinese investment in Africa are typically unconditional, say not tie with political, economic and governance reforms. Whereas, investment of western countries and other donor agencies come with certain conditionalities.

Zweig and Jianhai (2005) explore that, China going global strategy is driven by its domestic development strategy and the need for resources. As, the china sole interest is not in natural resources. Several Chinese firms have ventured with manufacturing, services sector and with telecom sectors. Because of that, African heaving with low-cost Chinese motorcycles and electronics goods which is beneficial for consumers in the continent.

In Jan 2006, Chinese government officially announced policy for African countries to strengthen the establishment of new strategic partnership and to intensify economic cooperation with African countries. In Nov 2006, China-Africa high level summit was held in Beijing with participation of heads of state of 40 African countries to build trade and investment relations between the world fastest growing economy and world's poorest continents. As IMF (2006) examined that, China economic size in terms of Purchasing Power Parity (PPP) in 2005 was more than five time than sub-Saharan African countries. World Bank also estimated that GNI Per capita was \$745 in sub-Saharan African countries and with contrasted \$1740 in China in 2005.

Institutions is playing a significant role to build and enhance infrastructure development in the developed countries. Several African countries growth performance is poor with abundant natural resources. Leite and Weidman (1999) argued that, natural resource abundant countries creates an opportunity of rent-seeking behaviour, which is an important factor to determine country's level of corruption.

Anyanwu (2012) argued that, most of FDI goes to African countries which has positively affect infrastructure and hence raising the marginal product of capital. The FDI inflow improve the economic relationship with donor countries in the perspective of to attract FDI inflows. Good infrastructure is a key determinant to attract FDI inflows in developing countries. As the existing studies (Musila and Sigue; 2006 and Dupasquier and Osakwe; 2006) concluded that FDI inflows to Africa depend on improvement of infrastructure. In a similar line, Anyanwu and Erhijakpor (2004) indicate that, telecommunications infrastructure play a significant role to attract FDI inflows in African countries. Several existing studies (Gholami et al., 2006; and Dauti, 2008) examined that ICT infrastructure and availability of good infrastructure enhances to attract more FDI inflows in the developing countries.

Period from 1998 to 2009 FDI flows goes those countries which have abundant natural resources (oil, gas and mining) projects. FDI inflows to Africa decline from \$72 billion to \$59 billion in 2009 due to financial crisis (UNCTAD, 2010b). From 1979 to 2000, Chinese investment projects in Africa is accounted 64 percent in manufacturing (spinning, weaving textiles and agro processing) and in resource based countries (World Bank, 2004). In last few years, Chinese FDI in resource extraction (mining and petroleum) sectors have increased in accordance with demand of country's resource needs. Similarly, Chinese investment has surged in construction and infrastructure, as Chinese willing to enhance and modify low-cost quality roads.

Ayodele and Sotola (2014) argued that, Investment of Chinese MNCs in Africa is not a threat as they provide substantial benefit. Chinese government and its private investors willing to invest in those sectors where western are not ready to invest in such area like physical infrastructure and manufacturing. China investment in Africa has created long debated issue among policy makers and researchers in both developed and developing countries. Large number of existing studies argued that, china strong economic relationship with African countries is creating a situation what western countries already did to exploit its natural resources and governance. The keen interest of China in Africa is to explore opportunities and give them financial and development assistance. The aim of this development assistance is to provide technical assistance and infrastructure development. The Africa nationals consider china as an alternative institute like IMF and World Bank in terms of access to loan and projects funding (Zheng and Liang, 2010). African countries are not willing to rely on western foreign investments. Eckert (2013) concluded that from 2003-06 Chinese investment infrastructure development rose from \$1 billion to \$7 billion.

Cheung et al (2011) claim that, African natural rich rich countries have a positive impact on Chinese investment decision how much to invest in the country. An emerging economy of china is considered as a global capital provider. Cheung et al (2011) argued that, china invested \$844 billion in US treasury bills in June 2010, as a capital provider in developed as well as developing countries including Africa that are traditionally considered as a riskier and not usually favoured by western investors. In a similar line, UN report (UNCTAD, 2007) examine that china is the major capital providers to African developing countries. Furthermore, Besada et al. (2008) claim that, Africa has become the third largest recipient of Chinese ODI.

For instance, Brookes (2007) and Wand and Bio-Tchane (2008) concluded that, Chinese investment crowd out manufacturing industry in Africa, this will lead to adversely affect employment. Chinese investment created number of high quality jobs, while Chinese firms bring their own workers. Our empirical findings affirm the notion that seeking nature resources is a motivation behind China's overseas investment in Africa. The preferences are for countries with minerals and oil.

Whereas, Nnadozie and Osili (2004) examine that US FDI flow to Africa have no significant effect of good infrastructure on FDI inflows.

Empirical Analyses

Our objective is to analyse the impact of Chinese FDI on infrastructure development. To meet the objective, we work with panel data set of 28 African countries spanning from 2003-2015. We start our estimation with the following base-line model.

$$Infras_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 OFDI_{it} + \beta_2 X_{it} + \mu_i + v_t + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Infrastructure ($Infras_{it}$) is our dependent variable that further classified in five different variables namely, fixed telephone subscription, fixed broadband subscription, mobile cellular subscription, rail line and investment in transports; Chinese FDI ($OFDI_{it}$) is our variable of interest. X_{it} is the vector of control variables namely, FDI inflows, public savings and private participation in infrastructure development. Whereas μ_i and v_t denotes unobserved cross-sectional and time specific effects respectively, ε_{it} is the error term.

Empirical Results

As mentioned in the introductory part, the key objective of this study is to examine the impact of Chinese FDI on infrastructure development in selected African countries. Hence, our empirical analysis mainly focuses on infrastructure development through Chinese investment in African countries.

Table 1 shows the estimated results of our model, shows a positive relationship between Chinese investment ($CFDI_{it}$) and infrastructure development ($Infras_{it}$), which are statistically significant at one percent. The results are in line with the empirical findings of Zafar (2007), Anyanwu (2012) and (Kumari and Sharma, 2015) they argued that, Chinese FDI is improved infrastructure quality in the African countries. As, these results not in favour of several existing studies claim that China sole interest is to extract natural resources from resource rich or abundant African countries. Zafar (2007) claim that, Chinese investment in the African oil sector has been mixed. While, one thing which is most important Chinese investment has positively contributed to finance several infrastructure projects in african poor and war conflict countries. Because, improved infrastructure is foundation for economic development in low-income economies to eradicate or mitigate poverty. In addition, Chinese investment played a positive role to improve infrastructure development in African countries (IMF, 2010; UNCTAD, 2010b).

Table A1: Fixed Effects Estimation Results

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
($InvTel_{it}$)				.04576** (1.89)	
($InvTransp_{it}$)			.0003 (0.023)		
($Saving_{it}$)	-0.00333 (-1.10)	-0.00508 (-1.62)	-0.0026 (-0.87)	-0.0036 (-1.00)	
($FDII_{it}$)	.0108** 2.23	.0120** (2.43)	.0110** (2.30)	.0109** (2.02)	
($PolStab_{it}$)	-0.013 (-1.34)	-0.00037 (-0.10)	-0.015*** (-1.17)	-0.004 (-0.33)	-0.015 (-1.17)
($Corrup_{it}$)			.00591 (1.01)		-0.0487** (-1.95)
($Regulatory_{it}$)	.062** (2.21)	.0106 (1.48)	-----	-----	-----
($Rule_{it}$)	-0.00217 (-0.32)	.083*** (4.32)	-----	-0.0033 (-0.48)	-----
($OFDI_{it}$)	.14451*** (7.25)	.14820*** (7.42)	.14572*** (7.30)	.1514*** (6.61)	-----
Hausman test	29.61	22.35	29.89	22.68	24.56
Prob	0.0001	0.009	0.000	0.007	0.006
No of Obs	239	239	308	411	308
SE of Reg	.34671	.3221	.065	.023	.065

Note: ***, **, * presents level of significance at 1%, 5% 10% respectively. The values of t-statistics are in parenthesis. The dependent variable is income inequality.

The variable (FDI_{it}) has a positive and significant impact on infrastructure development ($Infras_{it}$). The result in favour of Musila and Sigue (2006) concluded that good infrastructure is a good determinant to

attract FDI inflow in developing countries. Furthermore, (Anyanwu and Erhijakpor, 2004; and Dauti, 2008) claim that telecommunication and availability of good infrastructure lead to attract more FDI inflows in the developing countries.

The variable (Private participation rate) ($InvTel_{it}$) has a negative impact on infrastructure development ($Infras_{it}$), the results are not in line with the findings of Cerra et al. (2017) and Ranade (2001) argued that, an increase in the participation of private investment is positively contributed to the accumulation of infrastructure development. Similarly, public saving ($Saving_{it}$) has also a negative impact on infrastructure development in the sample countries. The results are inconsistent with the findings of Dao (2008) examined that, in countries have higher public saving rate are able to devote more resources to enhance infrastructure development. An increase in the public savings lead to increase the number of telephone subscription. Similarly, an increase in public saving lead to increase the length of roads per 1000 people.

Conclusion

Chinese investment played a vital role in infrastructure development of African countries. Foreign direct investment is an important contributing factor for both developed and developing countries. FDI is bring number of development benefits like increased exports, generate employment opportunities and improve infrastructure development. Furthermore, transfer of technology through FDI inflow to increase domestic productivity and will led to generate employment in the existing countries. Some of the factors like political instability deter infrastructure development in Africa. The study concludes that Chinese FDI stock has a significant positive effect on the infrastructure development in African countries.

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Appendix A

Table A1: Descriptive Statistics of Variables under Consideration

Variables	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev	Min	Max
(Infras _{it})	317	6.20e-09	1.000002	-39102	6.0976
(OFDI _{it})	362	4.416719	1.992949	-1.4276	8.6912
(InvTransp _{it}),	61	18.48323	1.573376	15.12384	22.20487
(Saving _{it})	274	17.79988	15.20105	-33.0414	80.728
(FDII _{it})	363	6.401957	10.09746	-5.977	89.47596
(PolStab _{it}),	364	37.82771	23.08233	2.415459	92.78846
(Corrup _{it})	360	33.24638	22.63405	.4739336	85.85366
(Regulatory _{it}),	364	31.62144	19.83767	.4807692	83.6538
(Rule _{it}),	364	32.15354	21.10976	.9389671	83.2535
(InvTel _{it}),	314	18.15841	1.76877	12.52453	21.8407

Appendix B

Table B1: Pooled OLS Estimation Results

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
(InvTel _{it}),	1.87*** (5.85)	1.57*** (5.12)	2.06*** (4.73)	2.17*** (6.25)	2.06*** (4.73)
(InvTransp _{it}),	.090 *** (5.06)	.087*** (5.06)	.063** (2.50)	.136*** (5.66)	.063** (2.50)
(Saving _{it})	.0035 (0.67)	.00008 (0.02)	.055** (2.02)	.025*** (2.67)	.055** (2.02)
(FDII _{it})	.0027 (0.33)	.00523 (0.63)	-.015*** (-1.17)	-.004 (-0.33)	-.015 (-1.17)
(PolStab _{it}),	.289*** (5.04)	-.0125*** (-2.95)	.387*** (4.26)	.251*** (3.11)	.387*** (4.26)
(Corrup _{it})	.00134 (0.20)	-----	-----	-----	-----
(Regulatory _{it}),	-----	.0071 (1.44)	-----	-----	-----
(Rule _{it}),	-----	-----	-.171** (-2.61)	-----	-----
(OFDI _{it})	.0033 (0.08)	-.0287 (-0.73)	-----	-.059** (-2.53)	-----
	-----	-----	-----	-----	-.171** (-2.61)
BP test	14.35	56.69	46.35	41.34	4.38
Prob	0.0002	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.036
No of Obs	239	239	199	199	308
SE of Reg	.027	.019	.065	.023	.065

Note: ***, **, *presents level of significance at 1%, 5% 10% respectively. The values of t-statistics are in parenthesis. The dependent variable is income inequality.

Table B1: Random Effects Estimation Results

Variables	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5
$(InvTel_{it})$,				.04576** (1.89)	2.06*** (4.73)
$(InvTransp_{it})$,	.090 *** (5.06)	.087*** (5.06)	.063** (2.50)	.136*** (5.66)	.063** (2.50)
$(Saving_{it})$	-.00333 (-1.10)	-.00448 (-1.44)	-.0023 (-0.79)	-.0032 (-0.91)	.055*** (2.02)
$(FDII_{it})$.0108** 2.23	.0111** (2.26)	.0105 (2.22)**	.0101** (1.88)	
$(PolStab_{it})$,	-.013 (-1.34)	-.00121 (-0.34)	-.015*** (-1.17)	-.004 (-0.33)	-.015 (-1.17)
$(Corrup_{it})$.289*** (5.04)	.256*** (4.47)	.00606*** (1.06)	.251*** (3.11)	.387*** (4.26)
$(Regulatory_{it})$,	.062** (2.21)	.0078 (1.22)	-----	-----	-----
$(Rule_{it})$,	-.00217 (-0.32)	.083*** (4.32)	-----	-.0042 (-0.68)	-----
$(OFDI_{it})$.14451*** (7.25)	.1436*** (7.18)	.14291*** (7.23)	.1473*** (6.40)	-----
ATR _{it}	-----	-----	-----	-.059** (-2.53)	-----
ETR _{it}	-----	-----	-----	-----	-.171** (-2.61)
BP test	31.42	37.76	4.38	7.24	4.38
Prob	0.00	0.00	0.036	0.007	0.036
No of Obs	239	239	308	199	308
SE of Reg	.34671	.3221	.065	.023	.065

Note: ***, **, *presents level of significance at 1%, 5% 10% respectively. The values of t-statistics are in parenthesis. The dependent variable is income inequality.

Appendix C

Table C1: List of Sampling Countries

Algeria	Angola	Botswana	Cameroon
Chad	Congo Rep	Equatorial	Ethiopia
Gabon	Ghana	Guinea	Kenya
Liberia	Libya	Madagascar	Malawi
Mali	Mauritania	Mauritius	Mozambique
Namibia	Nigeria	Senegal	Seychelles
South Africa	Togo		